

Studies on Polycyclic Compounds. Part II. Synthesis of Hexahydro-1:2-benzazulene

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1-Ketoindan-2- β -propionic acid was prepared from (a) 2-cyanohydrindan-1-one by cyanethylation and (b) by condensation of diethyl malonate with 2-morpholinomethyl-1-hydrindanone. The corresponding methyl ester was submitted to Stobbe condensation and the product through usual series of reaction converted into hexahydro-1,2-benzazulene.

In continuation of our work¹, the synthesis of hexahydro-1:2-benzazulene (viii) is described below.

Michael condensation² of acrylonitrile with 2-cyanohydrindan-1-one³ gave 1-keto-2-cyanoindan-2- β -propionitrile (I). This was hydrolysed and decarboxylated to give 1-ketoindan-2- β -propionic acid (II: R=H).

(I)

(II)

(III)

(IV)

(V)

(VI)

(VII)

(VIII)

1. Roy, *this Journal*, 1967, 44, 91.

2. Banerjee and Bhattacharyya, *this Journal*, 1958, 35, 467.

3. Johnson and Shelberg, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1945, 67, 1745.

This acid was also prepared from α -hydrindan-one via Mannich reaction. Condensation between 2-morpholinomethyl-1-hydrindan-one methiodide⁴ and diethyl malonate in absolute ethanol in the presence of sodium ethoxide proceeded smoothly to give ethyl 2'-ethoxycarbonyl- β -(1-oxo-2-indanyl) propionate (III). This was hydrolysed and decarboxylated to yield 1-ketoindan-2- β -propionic acid (II: R=H). This acid was prepared before by von Braun and Manz⁵ and also by Ansell and Hey⁶.

The keto-ester (II: R=Me) was subjected to the Stobbe condensation^{7,8} with dimethyl succinate; the product on esterification gave the triester (IV). The ester was hydrolysed and decarboxylated by the hydrobromic acid method^{7,9} to give 1-2'-carboxyethyl-2-2'-carboxyethylindane (V: R=H); the endocyclic structure is preferred from analogy⁸. The ester (V: R=Me) was hydrogenated over 10% Pd/C and product hydrolysed to 1-2'-carboxyethyl-2-2'-carboxyethylindane (VI: R=H). The ring closure of the diacid to 9:10-benzbicyclo-[5:3:0] deo-9-en-4-one (VII) was carried out by thermal decomposition in the presence of fine iron powder and of a small amount of crystalline barium hydroxide according to the method of Sorm¹⁰. The ketone was reduced with sodium borohydride and the crude alcohol was dehydrated with potassium bisulphate to yield hexahydro-1:2-benzazulene (VIII). The formation of two isomers with the double bond in either 5- or 6-position may be assumed. Dehydrogenation of this unsaturated hydrocarbon to 1:2-benzazulene can be effected by standard procedures¹⁰⁻¹¹ but could not be carried out because of the paucity of material.

EXPERIMENTAL*

1-Keto-2-cyanoindan-2- β -propionitrile (I). To a solution of sodium ethoxide, prepared from sodium (0.012 g.) and absolute ethanol (2.4 ml), cooled in ice-salt mixture for 30 min., was added dropwise with continuous stirring a solution of 2-cyanohydrindan-1-one³ (3.14 g.) in dry ethanol (20 ml). The solution was cooled for further 15 min., and then acrylonitrile (1.06 g.) was added dropwise in course of 30 min. with vigorous stirring. The pale yellow reaction mixture was allowed to stand at room temperature for 16 hr. The mixture was acidified with HCl and poured in large excess of water. The pale yellow crystalline solid was filtered and washed successively with cold water, saturated sodium bicarbonate solution and cold water and dried; yield, 3.41 g. (81%), m.p. 116°-112°. A portion of this was crystallised from ethanol, m.p. 112°. (Found: C, 74.27; H, 4.76; N, 13.33. C₁₃H₁₆ON₂ requires C, 74.27; H, 4.79; N, 13.32%).

4. Harradence and Lions, *J. Proc. Roy. Soc., N.S. Wales*, 1939, 72, 284; *Chem. Abs.*, 1939, 33, 6825.
5. Von Braun and Manz, *Annalen*, 1929, 468, 258.
6. Ansell and Hey, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, 2874.
7. Johnson *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, 72, 2395.
8. Bhattacharyya *et al.*, *this Journal*, 1964, 41, 479.
9. Sen *et al.*, *this Journal*, 1958, 35, 751.
10. Sorm, *Collection Czechoslov. Chem. Commun.*, 1947, 12, 251.
11. Nunn and Rapson, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, 1051.

*All m.p.s. and b.p.s. are uncorrected. The U. V. absorption spectra were recorded on Unicam spectrophotometer SP. 500.

1-Ketoindan-2-β-propionic acid (II: R=H).—The dinitrile (11.5g.) was refluxed for 26 hr. with a mixture of HCl (conc., 60 ml) and glacial acetic acid (25 ml). Acids were removed under reduced pressure; the residue, after cooling, was diluted with water and taken in ether; the ethereal layer was extracted with saturated sodium bicarbonate solution. The alkaline extract was acidified with HCl (cold, conc.) and the faint yellow solid was again extracted with ether. The ethereal layer was washed with little water and dried (Na₂SO₄). Removal of the solvent gave a yellowish acidic product (4.30 g., 88.5%), crystallised from a mixture of benzene and petroleum (40-60°), m.p. 106-8° (lit.⁵ 106-8°).

Ethyl 2'-ethoxycarbonyl-β-(1-oxo-2-indanyl)propionate. (III)—To a solution of sodium ethoxide, prepared from sodium (1.8 g.) and dry ethanol (47 ml), cooled in ice, was added diethyl malonate (11.4g.) rapidly with constant shaking and left at room temperature for 1 hr. The methiodide of 2-morpholinomethyl hydrindan-1-one⁴ (20 g.) was added to the ethyl sodiomalonate and refluxed for 5 hr. Most of the alcohol was removed under water suction and the residue was poured in cold water (50 ml). It was then extracted thrice with ether, the ethereal layer was washed with cold water and dried (Na₂SO₄). Solvent was distilled off under reduced pressure and the residue was distilled to afford the desired product (6 g., 38.4%), b.p. 170-75°/4 mm.

1-Ketoindan-2-β-propionic acid (II: R=H).—The preceding product (3 g.) was saponified with KOH solution (20%, 12 ml) by refluxing for 4 hr. After usual working up, the residue (2.17 g.) was decarboxylated at 185-95° in an oil bath until the evolution of gas ceased (20 min.). The product was taken in ether; ether layer was extracted with saturated sodium bicarbonate solution. The alkaline extract was acidified with HCl (cold, conc.) and extracted with ether. The ethereal layer was washed with little water and dried (Na₂SO₄). On removal of solvent, the residue was evaporatively distilled at 160-65°/0.4 mm to furnish pure material (1 g., 50.2%), m.p. 85-90°. It was crystallised from a mixture of benzene and petroleum (40-60°), and had m.p. 106-8° (lit.⁶ 106-8°). Mixed m.p. with the sample described above, was undepressed.

Methyl-β-(1-Keto-2-indanyl) propionate (II: R=Me).—The above acid (5.6g.) was esterified by an ethereal solution of diazomethane, prepared from nitrosomethyl urea (5.8 g.), b.p. 140°/0.4 mm, yield 5 g. (90%). A portion of the ester was evaporatively distilled at 140°/0.4 mm to afford a colourless oil. (Found: C, 71.33; H, 6.33. C₁₃H₁₄O₃ requires C, 71.54; H, 6.47%).

1-1', 2'-Bis-(methoxycarbonyl) ethylidene-2-2'-methoxycarbonylethylindane (IV). — Dimethyl succinate (4.814 g., 0.033 mole) was added slowly during $\frac{1}{2}$ hr., under nitrogen, to a solution of potassium (0.585 g., 0.015 g. atom) in dry t-butanol (11 ml) at room temperature. The yellow homogeneous mixture was added to the foregoing keto-ester (3.27 g., 0.015 mole) within $\frac{1}{2}$ hr. and the deep red solution was left at room temperature for 16 hr. The reaction mixture was then acidified with HCl (cold, dilute) and worked up in the usual way. The gummy acid (3 g.) was esterified with diazomethane, prepared from nitrosomethyl urea (2.71 g.), to furnish the trimethyl ester as a straw coloured oil (2.1 g., 40%), b.p. 183-85°/0.3 mm. A portion of the ester was evaporatively distilled at 160°/0.2 mm, to afford a colourless oil, λ_{max} 270 mμ (ε, 12590). (Found: C, 66.38; H, 6.64. C₁₉H₂₀O₆ requires C, 65.88; H, 6.40%).

1-2'-*Carboxyethyl-2-2'-carboxyethylindene* (V: R=H).—The preceding unsaturated ester (14 g.) was refluxed for 6 hr. with a mixture of glacial acetic acid (175 ml), HBr (48%; 240 ml) and water (70 ml). The acids were removed under reduced pressure; the residue, after cooling, was diluted with water and extracted with ether. After usual working up, the crude dibasic acid (11.28 g.) on trituration with ether provided crystalline solid, m.p. 163-67°. A portion of the acid was crystallised from a mixture of ether and petroleum (60-80°), m.p. 160-70°, $\lambda_{\max}$ 258 m μ (ϵ , 13860). (Found: C, 69.60; H, 6.36. $C_{16}H_{16}O_4$ requires C, 69.22; H, 6.20%).

1-2'-*Methoxycarbonylethyl-2-2'-methoxycarbonylethylindene* (V: R=Me).—The crude dibasic acid (11 g.) was esterified with a mixture of dry methanol (80 ml) and H_2SO_4 (conc. 8 ml) by refluxing for 48 hr., b.p. 170°/0.4 mm, yield 10 g. (90%). A portion was evaporatively distilled at 120°/0.2 mm to afford analytical sample, $\lambda_{\max}$ 263 m μ (ϵ , 11190). (Found: C, 70.33; H, 6.88. $C_{17}H_{20}O_4$ requires C, 70.81; H, 6.99%).

1-2'-*Methoxycarbonylethyl-2-2'-methoxycarbonylethylindane* (VI: R=Me).—The unsaturated ester (V: R=Me; 5.4 g.) was hydrogenated in 95% ethanol (120 ml) over 10% Pd/C (300 mg.). Removal of catalyst and solvent furnished the saturated ester (5.4 g., 99%), b.p. 130°/0.4 mm. (Found: C, 70.23; H, 7.55. $C_{17}H_{22}O_4$ requires C, 70.32; H, 7.64%).

1-2'-*Carboxyethyl-2-2'-carboxyethylindane* (VI: R=H).—The foregoing dimethyl ester (5 g.) was saponified with a mixture of KOH (1.5 g.), water (1 ml) and methanol (40 ml) by refluxing for 4 hr. After usual working up a brown gummy residue (4.5g.) was obtained.

9-10-*Benzbicyclo [5:3:0] dec-9-en-4-one* (VII).—An intimate mixture of the crude dibasic acid (VI; R=H; 1.31 g., 0.005 mole), crystalline barium hydroxide (0.1 g.) and iron powder (1.10 g., 0.02 mole), on pyrolysis at 300° in N_2 atmosphere, afforded the ketone. This was purified by evaporative distillation at 160°/0.2 mm; yield, 600 mg (60%). The material was evaporatively distilled again at 100°/0.2 mm to afford an analytical sample. (Found: C, 83.89; H, 8.22. $C_{14}H_{16}O$ requires C, 83.96; H, 8.05%).

The 2,4-DNP, m.p. 167-61° was purified through chromatography and crystallisation from a mixture of benzene and methanol, and had m.p. 184-85°. (Found: N, 14.62. $C_{16}H_{16}O_4N_4$ requires N, 14.73%).

Hexahydro-1:2-benzazulene (VIII).—The solution of ketone (VII; 500 mg.) in minimum volume of ethanol (3.5 ml) and water (2 drops) was cooled and $NaBH_4$ (200 mg.) was added. The mixture was stirred for 6 hr. at 20°. The reaction mixture was then decomposed with acetic acid (2 ml) diluted with water and extracted with ether. The ethereal extract was washed with sodium bicarbonate solution and little water and dried (Na_2SO_4). Solvent was removed and the residual crude alcohol (500 mg) was dehydrated by heating, under an air condenser for 20 min. at 180°, with freshly fused potassium bisulphate (500 mg.) The mixture was cooled and the hydrocarbon was taken in ether; the ethanol solution was washed with water and dried (Na_2SO_4). On removal of solvent, the residue was evaporatively distilled at 65°/0.2 mm, yield (200 mg.) 56%. A portion of the hydrocarbon was evaporatively distilled again at 65°. 2 mm to afford a colourless oil; the olefinic compound responded to tetranitromethane test. (Found: C, 90.85; H, 8.95. $C_{14}H_{16}$ requires C, 91.25; H, 8.75%).

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